

JURISPRUDENCE

ISSUES OF APPLICATION OF INSTITUTIONS OF JUSTICE OF THE PEACE AND JURY TRIALS IN AZERBAIJAN (HISTORICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS)

Ismayilov Kh.

Baku State University, Department of Theory and History of State and Law, Prof.Dr.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11097492>

Abstract

Against the background of increasing trends in the formation and strengthening of the foundations of the rule of law state and civil society, the role and importance of judicial and legal institutions, among which justice of the peace and jury trials occupy a certain place, are becoming increasingly clear. The introduction of these institutions in the post-Soviet space was first carried out in the second half of the XIX century on the basis of the judicial charters of 1864. But in contrast to the institute of justice of the peace, which was applied throughout the territory of the former Russian Empire (although for the outskirts of the empire were provided some deviations from the principles enunciated in the judicial statutes), the institution of a jury was introduced only in the central part of the state. The article makes an effort to expose the historical and legal analysis of issues related to the use of the institutes of justice of the peace and jury in Azerbaijan in the specified period, and also reveals the legal nature and characteristic features of these judicial and legal institutions. For this purpose, archival, legislative and publicistic sources were used. On the basis of the conducted analysis through the use of various legal methods, primarily the systemic, comparative and historical-legal methods, the estimation is given to process of realization of the relevant judicial legal institutions in the In the Russian Federation and the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: justice of the peace, jury trial, historical and legal aspect, judicial reform, magistrate court, mediation.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, in the post-Soviet space, discussions have been intensified on improving the national judicial system, carrying out reforms in this area and introducing new judicial institutions. Against the background of these discussions, many assumptions have been put forward regarding the formation (or restoration in an improved form) of the institutions of peace justice, jury trials, mediation, etc. Along with the fact that these institutions contribute to increasing the efficiency of the expected results from legal proceedings, they also provide for active participation of the public in the administration of justice, which makes this process more democratic.

After the gaining of independence of the post-Soviet states, their parliaments discussed and adopted laws providing for the introduction of many democratic institutions, which the dominant ideology under the previous government "branded" as "bourgeois" and denied them. Most of these democratic institutions are reflected in the constitutions of the respective states. At the same time, it should be emphasized that the legislative consolidation of democratic institutions and principles in the process of lawmaking in post-Soviet countries, among which progressive judicial and legal institutions occupy a special place, were not unified. For example, in Russia, the jury was restored in 1993. In Azerbaijan, the Law "On the Judicial System of the Republic of Azerbaijan" dated June 26, 1990 provided for the formation of a special court with an expanded collegium of assessors to consider serious criminal cases. On February 5, 1991, the legal force of this provision was temporarily suspended. With the Law "On Courts and Judges in the Republic of Azerbaijan" of June 10, 1997 (Chapter XXI, Articles 115-123) and the Criminal

Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan of July 14, 2000 (Chapter XLVI, Articles 359-380) the institution of the jury was reintroduced in the republic.

As for the institute of peace justice, in Russia the magistrates' courts were reorganized in 1998. But, in the opinion of many researchers, the current process of the formation of the magistrates' justice in the Russian Federation was incomplete due to the establishment of the dependence of the magistrate on the district court. And in Azerbaijan, despite the rich historical experience and the advancement of doctrinal proposals regarding the need to restore magistrates' courts, this issue has not yet found its legislative embodiment in the lawmaking activities of the legislative body - the Milli Mejlis of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Research objective and analytical data

The processes taking place at the present stage dictate the need for continuation of the judicial and legal reform and the beginning of a new stage in the development of the judicial and legal system in Azerbaijan and Russia. In this regard, the relevant normative acts are adopted, as well as amendments and additions to the existing legislative acts are made. On the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On deepening reforms in the judicial and legal system" dated April 3, 2019, recommendations were made to the Supreme Court, the Judicial-Legal Council, the Ministry of Justice and other structures to improve legislation in this area, increase the authority of the judiciary and strengthen in a society of trust in the courts, the study of international best practices related to alternative mechanisms for the execution of decisions of courts and other bodies and the expansion of means of out-of-court settlement of disputes related to entrepre-

neurial activity, the creation of a specialized commercial court, the use of the Electronic Court information system to increase accessibility and transparency justice, an increase in the total number of judges for the purpose of effective activities of courts and reduce the time for consideration of cases in courts, etc.

Despite the strengthening of the material and technical resources of the judiciary, the computerization of the work of judges, the creation of favorable conditions for the performance of their duties, quality of the work of the courts cannot be called high. There are opinions that the quality of the work of the courts is mainly expressed in the number of appealed decisions. Almost 100% of decisions of the courts of first instance are appealed to the courts of appeal. About 90% of decisions of the courts of appeal are appealed to the Supreme Court. Low confidence in the courts on the part of citizens is explained by the fact that they often do not satisfy well-founded claims. If the decisions of the courts were legally justified, then even in the event of a loss, citizens would understand that the ruling is fair. It is officially recognized that the number of acquittals in relation to convictions is approximately 1%, and this is a very low figure. But at the same time, it should be noted that acquittals serve as a barometer of the independence of the judiciary. The foregoing once again confirms the need to introduce such judicial and legal institutions as the jury and peace justice in Azerbaijan (and in Russia to improve their structure and activities) in order to ensure the participation of citizens themselves in the administration of justice by means of jurors and the expansion of the conciliation process with the help of justices of the peace. ... The establishment of a jury will ultimately lead to an increase in the number of acquittals, strengthening the independence of judges.

The main advantages of a jury trial, in comparison with other forms of trial, are recognized as its independence from pressure from powerful individuals or representatives of the authorities and knowledge of life. Seeking the fairest possible solution to each case, the jury softens the severity of the law, reconciling its demands with the demands of human justice. With the existence of outdated and cruel laws, the jury, acquitting the defendants, despite the fact of the crime, reveals disagreement between the law and the people's legal consciousness, and this often leads to a change in criminal legislation.

As one of the important institutions not only of justice, but also of civil society, the jury allows the development of such principles in legal proceedings as discretion, adversariality, objectivity, equality of parties, and the presumption of innocence. It contributes to the eradication of various kinds of stereotypes, and the growth of professionalism of the participants in the process.

The resumptive positive aspects of the institution of the jury trial is that it acts as the most important constitutional guarantee of human rights, first of all, access to fair justice; the guarantor of the independence of the judiciary, the independence of the court and the fairness of the judicial procedure; means of judicial reform, assessment of the fairness of laws and education of the

legal consciousness of the broad masses of the population. A democratic tendency prevails here, that is, representatives of the people are directly involved in the exercise of judicial power. There is a high degree of independence of the jury from the state and state prosecution. As a result, the conditions for the contest of the parties are more ensured (collegiality, the absence of a psychological accusatory bias, the lack of knowledge of the jury about the case materials, their independence from professional judges, the introduction of everyday common sense into justice).

At the same time, as a result of a critical analysis of this institution, we have to talk about some of the shortcomings of a jury trial. These shortcomings mainly boil down to the fact that the jury's legal incompetence leads to unpredictability of their decisions, which are based not on the law, but on personal impression. As a result, not the right wins, but the eloquent; juries are heavily influenced by the media; jury trials are expensive, cumbersome and slow [21]. Opponents of using the institution of jurors (who are judges of fact) most often refer to the low level of legal consciousness of citizens who, as jurors, will sometimes justify those who clearly deserve punishment. In practice, they argue, jury verdicts also depend on random factors. The jury has the right to recognize a person as innocent, despite the proof of the crime. So, in the case of Krasnina, accused of premeditated murder of her partner (Ivanovo region), the jury decided: "Not guilty, although she did." Obviously, their verdict was influenced by data on the victim's personality, on his abuse of the defendant, etc. And in the Moscow region, in the case of P., who received a bribe in the amount of \$ 1,500, the jury, having recognized this as proven, found the defendant innocent, since he has a sick wife [22].

In some post-Soviet countries, there are other forms of an expanded jury when considering court cases. For example, in Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan, *aksakal courts* have been functioning for several years (according to experts, quite well), which is also a jury trial in its own way. They are given the right to resolve family and everyday disputes [22]. Despite the effectiveness of such "*people's courts*", nevertheless, these courts cannot completely replace the classical or continental forms of jury trials, which are mainly organized to consider serious criminal cases and provide for broad participation in the administration of justice of various segments of the population.

The institution of justices of the peace is also important for achieving the goals set by society for the judiciary. The primary task of these courts, which are closest to the population, is to reconcile the litigants. Thus, they contribute to the quick resolution of disputes, reducing the excessive workload of general courts. The revival of the institute of magistrates' courts in Azerbaijan and Russia has objective reasons. Among them, one can name the correspondence of the status of a magistrate to the tendencies of deepening specialization, professionalization of judges and the division of competence between courts of various levels; the desirability of resolving conflict situations through the active use of conciliation procedures; bringing justice

closer to the population with the introduction of elements of public control over the judicial system; the need to exempt courts of general jurisdiction from considering insignificant cases due to the increase in the number of appeals to the courts.

After the revival of magistrates' courts in Russia, there has been an increase in the number of appeals to these courts. On the one hand, this is due to the growth of confidence in them by the population, on the other hand, it gives rise to the problem of the insufficient number of justices of the peace. So, if in 2006 justices of the peace accepted 5 million 533 thousand civil claims for proceedings, and the number of cases considered by them to 486.7 thousand [17, p.142], now these figures have increased significantly. This is the case in the proceedings of administrative offenses considered by justices of the peace.

It should be noted that, at present, justices of the peace operate in many European states and the consideration of cases in these courts is carried out in the manner of simplified legal proceedings (summary offence). . And in some countries, for example in England, these courts function under the name "magistrate's court". The Magistrates' Courts, which are the most massive judicial bodies in the judicial system in England, are considered the most democratic. Official judicial statistics show that 95-98% of all court cases registered in the country are considered in magistrates' courts every year [8, p.1-2].

It should be noted that even in the second half of the 19th century, during the period of the implementation of judicial reform, in contrast to the jury, the introduction of world justice did not cause a serious socio-political reaction in the Russian Empire as a whole, including in the Azerbaijani provinces. With the reorganization of world justice in today's Russia, such a reaction was not observed either. Naturally, various points of view have been and are being expressed regarding this institution, but this has happened and is happening now only within the framework of a narrow professional discourse.

After the amendments were made to the 1997 Law on Courts and Judges, which provided for the abolition of the jury in Azerbaijan, as well as the exclusion of provisions on the functioning and powers of jurors from the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan, discussions about the usefulness or the uselessness of this institution do not subside. Some people say that "the institution of the jury is more suitable for Western countries than for Azerbaijan" [20], or "incapable people suddenly become arbiters of destinies. Citizens inhabiting the country must mature for a jury trial. To mature morally. To mature spiritually. "They will choose!" Let me ask you, who will choose? Find an incorruptible person to be selective. If you find him, you can appoint him as a judge. The jury will no longer be needed. The main problem of a corrupt society is not to find an honest person, but to find someone who will find an honest person"[19]. Others argue that "while the country is undergoing judicial reforms, the provision of jury trials cannot be excluded from legislation. If in the process of the ongoing reforms the uselessness of the jury trial became obvious, then in this case this

institution could be abolished. A jury trial would prevent corruption from spreading. Indeed, in ordinary courts, justice is in the hands of only a judge, a prosecutor and a lawyer. From this point of view, the participation of representatives of the general public in court proceedings would contribute to the observance of justice"[20].

These discussions once again show that there is no single opinion among theorists and practitioners about the institution of jurors. It should be noted that in some post-Soviet countries, including Azerbaijan, the modern problems of the establishment and functioning of the jury, its criticism to a large extent coincides with the opinions of opponents of the introduction of this institution in the 19th - early 20th centuries. Therefore, it is necessary to turn our attention to the problems of the formation of the legislative base and the application of this institution in Azerbaijan during the indicated historical periods. At the same time, examining the historical and legal aspects of the introduction of the institute of peace justice in Azerbaijan, we will try to substantiate the revival of magistrates' courts at the present stage of development of the judicial system, taking into account the historical experience.

Justice of the peace and jury trial during the period of Russian rule in Transcaucasia

The institute justice of the peace, introduced on the territory of the Transcaucasia, in particular Azerbaijan during the period of Russian rule on the basis of the judicial statutes of 1864, had its own distinctive features. So, as a result of promulgation of the Judicial Charters to the Azerbaijani provinces in two years after the adoption, in February 1868 district courts and magistrates' offices (the so-called magistrates' courts) were formed on the basis of the "Regulations on the Application of Judicial Charters on November 20, 1864 in the Transcaucasian Territory" of November 22, 1866 [13, 43880]. The purpose of introducing the institute of world justice was the successful experience of Western countries in using justices of the peace as the lowest level of the judicial system to resolve minor cases; the difficult socio-economic situation in the Russian Empire, namely, the formation of capitalist relations and changes in the social structure of society; political changes aimed at democratizing Russian society; congestion of district courts; lack of professional judges and people with higher legal education; changes in public consciousness due to the capitalization of economic relations; distrust of the people to the old tsarist judicial system. The introduction of the magistrate's court as the lowest level of the judicial system for solving certain problems was previously used in the world practice of reforming the judicial system. Thus, the institution of the "world court" appeared in England and successfully administered justice until the 1980s. France adopted the principles of building of justice of peace only in the 18th century, but without receiving the expected results, the French legislator made some changes and henceforth the magistrate's court became the lowest level of the judicial system. It was in this form that Germany and the Russian Empire familiarize with the magistrate court. Unlike the central provinces of Russia,

where the magistrate's court was isolated from the general judicial system, in Azerbaijan the magistrate's court was included in the unified judicial system. In other words, the separateness of the two judicial systems: world justice and common court places, has not been embodied in Azerbaijan. Congresses of justices of the peace representing a second court of law for their departments in the inner provinces of Russia were not established. Therefore, in the Azerbaijani provinces, the district court acted as an appellate instance in cases considered by justices of the peace. District and honorary justices of the peace were not subject to election, but to appointment as governor in the Caucasus. The term for the appointment of district justices of the peace was not set, and honorary justices of the peace were appointed for three years. The jurisdiction of the justices of the peace of Azerbaijan in comparison with the jurisdiction of the justices of the peace of the central provinces of Russia has been expanded. So, if in the internal provinces of Russia civil disputes could be resolved by the magistrates' courts only for an amount of up to 500 rubles, and criminal cases for which, according to the law, reprimands, fines up to 300 rubles, arrest up to 3 months were provided, then the jurisdiction of the magistrates' courts of Azerbaijani provinces included all civil cases on movable and immovable property worth not more than 2,000 rubles, cases of seizure and personal grievances and, finally, criminal cases in respect of which the law did not provide for punishment related to the deprivation or restriction of the rights of the state. In addition, the justices of the peace were entrusted with the production of the preliminary investigation, as well as the management of guardianship and the performance of notarial acts in those areas where there were no notaries [9, p.89-90].

District courts exercised direct supervision over justices of the peace, liable for the adoption of measures to restore the broken order in the world institutions and to bring the perpetrators to justice on the basis of Article 250 of the Charter of judicial institutions.

Regardless of the submission of a systematic annual report, the magistrates' courts were obliged to submit to the district courts for every third (quarterly) list of reports on the number of cases remaining from the previous third, on the number of cases received and resolved during the reporting period, both in criminal and civil cases, and on investigations and writs of execution with an exact designation of the number of cases pending and completed by each official separately, so that these reports are considered each time in the general meeting of the court with the participation of the prosecutor [1, op.5, d.20, ll. 23-23v.].

The appointment of justices of the peace as governor, and after some time as the minister of justice with the consent of the *chief civilian unit* in the Caucasus, imposing the duties of judicial investigators on justices of the peace and their assistants, non-establishment of congresses of justices of the peace, consideration of cases in district courts without the participation of jurors, etc. not only proceed from the basic principles of the judicial statutes of 1864, as some authors mistakenly believed [5, p.62], but were significant deviations from these principles.

On June 15, 1912, the Russian Empire adopted a law on the reform of the local court, which also related to the institute of justice of peace [16, p.967]. This law, which came into force on January 1, 1913, along with other issues, provided for the status of the magistrate's court as an elective, general civil social stratum with the involvement of "local people", allowing the use of customary law and local languages; to organize congress of justices of the peace, as a link between the local court and national judicial institutions. But, unfortunately, this reform covered only the central and western parts of the empire, and its outskirts, including the Azerbaijani provinces, were again remained out of sight.

For the first time, information about the jury trial in the history of the judicial system of Azerbaijan can be marked out during the implementation of the judicial reform of 1864. When applying the judicial statutes of November 20, 1864 in the Transcaucasian region, in particular in the Azerbaijani provinces, on the basis of "Regulations on the application of judicial charters on November 20, 1864 in the Transcaucasian region" dated November 22, 1866 [13, 43880] and "Decree on the introduction of judicial statutes to the Transcaucasian region from January 1, 1868" [13, 46374], under the guise of the peculiarities of this region and, mainly, the "underdevelopment" of the local population, a number of significant deviations from the general order of the judicial system and legal proceedings were envisaged.

Although the Establishment of Judicial Regulations and the Charter of Criminal Procedure provided for the formation of a public element in court across the Russian Empire in the second half of the 19th century, the introduction of such democratic elements as the institution of jury trials and the selectivity of world institutions did not find their legislative embodiment in Azerbaijan.

This was also facilitated by the arguments of the local bureaucracy regarding the introduction of a jury trial in Transcaucasia. Some of them categorically opposed this institution, believing that our people are not sufficiently developed to enter into considerations that require both subtle analysis and logical conclusions, others believed that it is of a "political nature", and therefore its introduction could cause undesirable consequences. But all of them agreed that the population of Transcaucasia allegedly "is too little aware of the crime of those incidents that horrify an educated society, and that this population, sitting in the courts, would completely justify all hardened criminals" [14, p.78] ...

The statements of the tsarist officials that the concepts of the local population about the crime of blood revenge, robberies, and the abduction of women do not correspond to the basic concepts of public safety, that these and other grave crimes almost belong to the very life of the inhabitants of the Caucasus, were gross slander and expressed the chauvinistic policy of the tsarist authorities in relation to "non-Russians". In addition, these statements were in contradiction with the data even of official statistics, which testified to the fact that the prevalence of crimes in the Transcaucasian provinces was about the same, and sometimes even less than

in the inner provinces of Russia. According to the results of the same statistics for 1879, it can be seen that one major crime within the jurisdiction of the district court in the Ganja (Elisabethpol governorate) accounted for 315 people, in the Tiflis province - for 322 people, in the Iravan province - for 484 people, whereas in the Odessa district - by 416 people, in the district of the St. Petersburg district chamber - by 344 people. [14, p.81-82]. On the other hand, these official data also did not reflect the actual state of affairs, because, along with criminal offenses, they also reflected manifestations of the struggle of the working peasantry in the form of the movement of the *kachags* (fugitives) against the tsarist officials, officers and local oppressors, who were characterized by Russian noble jurists as "robbery and plundering".

After the establishment of crown courts for criminal cases in Azerbaijan, as well as throughout the entire territory of Transcaucasia, since February 19, 1868, the central and local authorities became convinced of the unsuitability of these courts and the need to reform them by involving a public element. At the same time, they did not address a court of jury, but began to look for another form of court, significantly limiting the representation of the population by the most "reliable persons". This was the result of various projects, such as the project on the need to introduce "local knowledgeable people" into the Caucasian courts, drawn up by the chief in the Caucasus; the draft of the Prosecutor of the Tiflis Court of Justice "On the introduction of honorary members from local residents into the composition of the district courts of the Caucasian district"; the draft "On the formation of a mixed collegium of three members of the district court and three jurors of a special composition", developed by the commission for the revision of legal provisions on the judicial part, etc.

Some public and state leaders of that time had their own views on the application of the jury trial in the Transcaucasia. G.M. Tumanov, M.O. Gruzenberg and others advocated the introduction in areas where only crown courts operate, in particular in the Caucasus, not a jury of a special composition with an increase in educational and property qualifications and merging them into one collegium with by crown judges, as suggested by the Highly approved commission, and by jury of the general composition, that is, with the provision of representatives of all categories of the population.

In wide public circles of the Caucasus and in the periodicals, the idea was affirmed that the need for a jury trial is nowhere greater than in the Caucasus. The court here was too distant from the life of the population, from its legal and ethical views, from its everyday characteristics. In contrast to professional judges, whose a special legal education and professional activity placed in such living conditions that they did not have access to the necessary acquaintance with the various life conditions, the various circumstances in which crimes were committed, necessary for the correct resolution of cases, jurors who belonged to different representatives of society, knew the life of this latter in all its strata, with all the local characteristics and shades of each of the diverse groups that make up the society. Therefore, the introduction of the jury in Azerbaijan in

the native language of its inhabitants due to the insufficient prevalence of the Russian language (otherwise the jurors during the meeting on the question of the guilt and innocence of the defendant would often resort to the help of translators), would bring more benefit to society than the crown courts for criminal business.

The need to introduce a jury trial in Transcaucasia, in particular, in Azerbaijan, was determined by the extraordinary impressionability of the jury and their sensitivity to all the individual characteristics of each particular case. But the restrictions envisaged in the law when applying the judicial reform in Azerbaijan completely eliminated the local population from participating in the court. The authorities recognized that it was undesirable to create such a court in the Azerbaijani provinces in which judges, jurymen elected by the local population would be represented - who could, to a certain extent, limit or hinder the arbitrariness of judges appointed by the administration.

The conviction that only one possible reform of the criminal court operating in the region is the establishment of jury trial had been increasingly introduced in some official resolutions of various public organizations and in the periodicals. At that time, the attorney at the Tiflis Court of Justice M.O. Gruzenberg prepared a draft law "On the introduction of a jury in Transcaucasia", which proposed conducting legal proceedings in the native language of the local population with the participation of jurors [9, p.177-178]. The bill provided for such issues as the procedure for electing jurors, drawing up general and regular lists for their election; structure, rights and obligations of the Commission on compiling a list; the right of persons to file complaints about the incorrect inclusion or non-inclusion of someone in the general lists; the number of regular and reserve assessors included in the lists for each province; the procedure for calling jurors to participate in the consideration and resolution of criminal cases and many other issues.

However, the legal norms of the judicial charters that determined the procedure for the formation and operation of a jury trial (that the consideration of crimes entailing punishment combined with deprivation of all rights and benefits should take place in district courts with the participation of 12 elected jurors, who, by a majority vote, must to decide the question of the guilt or innocence of the defendant), had no legal force on the territory of Azerbaijan until the formation of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic in 1918.

The legal basis for the functioning of the institutes of justice of the peace and the jury during the period of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic (1918-1920)

During the functioning of the first democratic republic in Azerbaijan in 1918-1920 in all spheres of public, political and legal life of the country, major transformations took place, among which the reforms in the judicial system of the republic stood out. It was at this time that legal acts containing universal democratic values were adopted, in particular, a legal basis was created for the effective functioning of the judicial and investigative bodies. From the first days of its activity,

the Government of the Republic of Azerbaijan was engaged in the restoration of district, magistrates' courts and investigation departments that were inactive (in Ganja province) or liquidated (in Baku province) during the functioning of the previous authorities.

By a government decree of September 14, 1918, funds were allocated for the restoration of magistrates' courts within Azerbaijan [6, No. 9]. Due to the lack of trained specialists, the educational qualification was reduced and the minimum requirements for the replacement of judicial positions were established.

The Law "On Expanding the Jurisdiction of Magistrates' Courts in Criminal Cases and Changing Punishments for Certain Criminal Offenses Against Another's Property" of August 18, 1919 the jurisdiction of justices of the peace to consider and resolve criminal acts such as embezzlement, fraud and other theft of other people's property worth up to 10,000 manats (before that, stolen, embezzled or wasted property worth over 300 manats was under the jurisdiction of the district courts) was expanded. Along with this, the consideration of some criminal acts that belonged to the jurisdiction of the district courts and did not pose any particular public danger was transferred to the magistrates' courts [10, p.354-355].

Ad hoc subcommittee established on February 11, 1919 under the Ministry of Justice for the preparation of legal provisions "On local courts" with the aim of improving the local court in the Republic of Azerbaijan developed a draft law "On the Magistrates' Courts and People's Courts" [11, p.209-210]. In accordance with this draft law, the creation of courts of two types was envisaged: in cities, as well as in urban-type settlements - individual magistrates' courts; in other places - people's courts, built on the basis of the principle of collegiality (composed of three judges). Identity of the terms of reference was determined for both of these courts. As an appellate instance for these courts, the establishment of a general congress of justices of the peace and people's courts was envisaged, which included a special permanent chairman, one justice of the peace and one chairman of the people's court. The main criterion for the formation of these courts was the principle of eligibility, as well as educational qualifications. The latter was established for people's judges with an education of at least the fourth grade of city schools. And for the justices of the peace and the chairman of the people's court, the level of education should be higher.

Along with numerous laws, a draft law "On the establishment of a jury court in Azerbaijan" was prepared and adopted. Prepared by the subcommittee "On public involvement in the administration of justice", functioning under the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Azerbaijan since February 1919, the law (adopted by the Parliament of Azerbaijan at the beginning of 1920) provided for the establishment of a jury court in Azerbaijan, "on grounds significantly different from the foundations of jury trials in the former Russian Empire, and corresponding to local conditions and the latest advances in legal thought in Western Europe on this issue" [4, p.64]. According to this legal provision, the participation of the jury in solving all issues was envisaged,

both in making a verdict regarding the guilt or innocence of the defendant, and in deciding the issue of determining the punishment [11, p.292]. But the jurors, functioning under the previous regime, participated only in solving the issue of the guilt of the defendant and did not have the opportunity to influence the court in determining the punishment. Unfortunately, due to the conquest of Azerbaijan by the Bolsheviks, along with other democratic transformations, this institution could not be fully implemented.

Conclusion

In 1920, the Soviet power established in Azerbaijan abolished all democratically organized judicial bodies of the previous regime. Under the Soviets, justice was administered by a judge and two people's assessors. Formally, legally, all three of them had equal rights, but in practice, both in criminal and civil proceedings, the decision on the case was actually taken by a professional judge alone. As a disadvantage of the people's assessors, one can point to their inactivity, in which the collegiality of the decision was very conditional. As a rule, they uncomplainingly joined the verdict, unwittingly yielding to the authority of the judge.

During the last years of perestroika, in order to free the dependence of judges from local authorities, the idea of creating a jury was enshrined in Article 11 of the Fundamentals of Legislation of the USSR and the Union Republics on Judicial Proceedings of November 13, 1989. It is interesting that Azerbaijan was the pioneer of these processes. As part of the former USSR, Azerbaijan became the first union republic to establish a jury trial. Corresponding changes in the Criminal Procedure Code of the country were introduced by the Law of June 26, 1990 "On the judicial system of the Azerbaijan SSR". A 6-month period was provided for the organizational preparation of the creation of a jury, however, the action of the relevant articles of the Criminal Procedure Code was suspended by the Resolution of the Supreme Council of Azerbaijan "On the suspension of the entry into force of some articles of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan" dated February 9, 1991 and unfortunately, the jury did not commence their activity.

Subsequently, the adopted normative legal acts, in particular the "Law on Courts and Judges of the Republic of Azerbaijan" of 1997 and the "Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan" of 2000, provided for the relevant provisions regarding the organization and functioning of the jury, which, unfortunately, remained without effect and some time later they were excluded from the composition of these acts.

Nevertheless, in the post-Soviet countries, where jury courts function, their effectiveness has been proven in practice. For example, in Russia, juries have shown that they are more likely to pass acquittals than they do in the usual way. In 2017, out of 318 thousand defendants whose cases were considered by the court in a general manner, 67% (212 thousand) were convicted, 0.9% (2.9 thousand) were acquitted, in relation to 1.2% (3.9 thousand) on rehabilitating grounds and in relation to 28% (90 thousand) - on non-rehabilitating grounds the cases were terminated. 11% (23 thousand) courts

softened the charge. Taking into account the cases examined in a special order, in 2017, 0.3% of the defendants were acquitted. After jury verdicts in 2017, 446 people were convicted, 52 (10%) were acquitted. Over the past 10 years (2008–2017), jury trials have considered 4139 criminal cases. According to their verdicts, 7680 people (83%) were convicted, 1544 (16%) were acquitted [23]. Therefore, the authorities considered it necessary to expand the jurisdiction of the jury. After the restoration of the institution of jurors, there was a gradual narrowing of the competence of these courts (for example, in 2008–2013, articles such as "Terrorism", "Hostage-taking", "Riots", "Espionage", "Organization of a criminal community", "Murder", "Production and sale of drugs on a large scale", "Rape and sexual crimes against children", "Attempts on the life of public figures, law enforcement officers, judicial authorities", etc. Therefore, until June 1, a small number of crimes were attributed to the jurisdiction of the jury), but recently, at the initiative of representatives of civil society, in particular the Ombudsman and members of the Human Rights Council, who relying on practical achievements of effective results in the administration of justice with the participation of an expanded jury assessors, as well as with the initiation of this issue by the President of the Russian Federation regarding the need to expand the role of the institution of the jury, amendments were made to the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation and came into force on June 1, 2018. These amendments provide not only for the return of previously withdrawn criminal cases to the jurisdiction of the jury, but also for the extension of the jury to district and garrison courts. In addition to the jurisdiction of the jury, criminal cases under Part 1 of Art. 105 (murder without aggravating circumstances) and part 4 of Art. 111 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation (deliberate infliction of grievous bodily harm, resulting in the death of the victim) are included. Thus, according to experts, the number of cases considered with the participation of juries in Russia may increase 70 times - up to 15 thousand per year [24].

Due to the fact that in Russia (on the basis of the federal law of July 27, 2010, which entered into force on January 1, 2011) and Azerbaijan (on the basis of the law of March 29, 2019, which entered into force on April 4, 2019) laws on mediation have been adopted to regulate alternative dispute settlement procedures with the participation of a moderator (mediator), and the need to improve (or restore in Azerbaijan) the activities of world justice has increased even more. Because, along with other professional moderators, justices of the peace are also actively involved in reconciliation procedures, i.e. practical application of the mediation procedure. Using conciliation procedures and achieving reconciliation of the parties in the process, the judge achieves the main goal - a fair resolution of the dispute. It would not be superfluous to recall the fact that during the period of the initial application of peace justice in Russia and Azerbaijan in the magistrates' court of that time, alternative dispute resolution, which had features similar to modern mediation, should have become widespread. So, the magistrate's court from the moment

of its initial functioning should first of all try to reconcile the litigants.

Considering that judicial and legal reforms are continuing in Azerbaijan and various models and judicial and legal institutions are being actively discussed, we consider it necessary to consider at the legislative level the issue of the feasibility of restoring the institutions of peace justice and the jury in Azerbaijan (and in Russia, improvement of these institutions), taking into account historical experience of our countries. At the same time, when solving the problem of integration of the magistrate and jury into the proceedings, it is necessary to take into account modern restorative approaches to resolving legal conflicts. The revival and development of the magistrate court and the jury in this direction would help to improve the quality of their level in the administration of justice accessible to the people.

References:

1. Laws and regulations. State Historical Archives of the Republic of Azerbaijan (SHARA). Funds: 100, 169, 170, 894, 895.
2. Laws of the Azerbaijan SSR and decrees of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Azerbaijan SSR (1985–1991). Baku, 1991.
3. Azerbaijan Democratic Republic (1918–1920): Legislative acts (Collection of documents). Baku: "Azerbaijan". 1998, 560 p.
4. Address-calendar of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 1920, Ed. A.M. Stavrovsky. Baku, 1919–1920, 588 p., P. 64.
5. Agayan S.P. Peasant reform in Azerbaijan in 1870, Baku, 1956.
6. Newspaper "Azerbaijan". 1918, October 12, No. 9.
7. Gruzenberg M.O. Jury trial in Transcaucasia, Tiflis, 1917.
8. Derbyshire P. English Legal System in a Nutshell. London, 1995, p. 1–2.
9. Ismayilov Kh.J. Organization and activity of the judiciary in Azerbaijan in the 19th century. M.: "High school", 2003, 188 p.
10. Ismayilov Kh.J. History of Law of Azerbaijan. Baku: "Science and Education", 2015, 572 p. (in Azerbaijani),
11. Ismayilov Kh.J. The state of law of Azerbaijan Democratic Republic. Baku: "Science and Education", 2018, 332 p. (in Azerbaijani) /
12. Milman A.Sh. The political system of Azerbaijan in the XIX - early XX centuries, Baku: Azerne-shr, 1966, 320 p.
13. Complete Collection of Laws of the Russian Empire (CCLRE), vol. XLII, article 43880; Article 46374.
14. Tumanov G.M. Land issues and crime in the Caucasus, St. Petersburg, 1900.
15. Tumanov G.M. Robberies and court reform in the Caucasus, St. Petersburg, 1903.
16. Verniaev I.I. 'The Reform of Local Court of 1912 in Imperial Dimension: The Making of Common Institutes in Plural Society', Modern History of Russia, vol. 8, no. 4, 2018, pp. 966–982, p. 967; <https://>

doi.org/10.21638/11701/spbu24.2018.412 (In Russian).

17. Vetrov P. V., Kuznetsov I. A. World justice in the system of modern justice // Law and Society, 2013, No. 12 (058), pp. 140-145 /

18. Encyclopedia of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic. In 2 volumes. Baku: "Leader", vol. 1, 2004, 440 p; vol. 2, 2005, 472 p.

19. <https://www.disput.az/topic/308243>.

20. <http://interfax.az/view/612109>.

21. http://www.kalinovsky-k.narod.ru/p/krat_kurs/22-1.htm.

22. <https://works.doklad.ru/view/IK5Bd5Hf9Os.html>.

23. <https://tass.ru/obschestvo/3812750>

24. <https://tass.ru/obschestvo/5251793>.